

Physical localization of *phyA* and *rbcS* genes in rice

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Phytochrome is an important photoreceptor and regulates many growth and development processes in plants (Thompson and White 1991, Furuya 1993, Terzaghi and Cashmore, 1995). Ribulose-1.5-bisphosphate carboxylase (Rubisco) small subunit genes (*rbcS*) are regulated developmentally by light (Tobin and Silverthorne 1985, Gilmarin et al 1990). Both genes (*phyA* and *rbcS*) coding for phytochrome and Rubisco SSU are functionally related. We tried to physically map onto the chromosomes by in situ hybridization rice genes related to photoperiod / light reception, signal transduction, and gene expression regulated by photoperiod, aiming to understand the relationship between the structure and function of the rice genome and between the genetic map and the physical map. The physical locations of CaM and Ca²⁺-ATPase genes were reported (Bi et al 1996). The results of those of *phyA* and *rbcS* genes follow.

The rice *phyA* gene clone, pPHY1, and *rbcS* gene clone, pRR1, are genomic clones of 6.6 kb and 1.1 kb in size, kindly provided by Prof. Nam-Hai Chua of Rockefeller University and Prof. Ray Wu of Cornell University, USA. *Oryza sativa* L. subsp. *indica*, cv. Guang-lu-ai 4, was used for chromosome preparations. Clones pPHY1 and pRR1 were transformed into *E. coli* TGI. Plasmid amplification, extraction, labeling with biotin, in situ hybridization, and detection were performed with the procedures followed by Bi et al (1996). Chromosomes were identified according to data from Kurata (1986).

The results showed that the hybridization detection ratio was about 29.79% for *phyA* and 21.56% for *rbcS*. The *phyA*

Chromosome locations and detection ratios of *phyA* and *rbcS* genes in rice.

Clone name	Size (kb)	Chromosome location ^a	Average detection ratio (%)
<i>phyA</i>	6.6	3L near centromere	14.89
		3S end	12.77
		3L middle	2.13
		Total	29.79
<i>rbcS</i>	1.1	7L near centromere	8.62
		5L end	6.90
		6L 2/3 distance from centromere	6.04
		Total	21.56

^aL = long arm, S = short arm.

Chromosome maps of rice *phyA* and *rbcS* genes showing hybridized positions. Short arm is at the top, constriction represents the centromere, and the long arm is under the constriction.

gene was located near the centromere of the long arm, at the end of the short arm, and in the middle of the long arm on chromosome 3. The *rbcS* gene was mapped near the centromere on the long arm of chromosome 7, at the end of the long arm of chromosome 5, and at the 2/3 distance of the long arm from the centromere in chromosome 6 (see table, figure).

The *phyA* gene was near RZ575 on chromosome 3 of the genetic map (Causse et al 1994), and RZ575 was on the long arm (Singh et al 1996). We also located the *phyA* gene on chromosome 3 and found three loci. This suggests that fragments for the *phyA* gene are dispersed on chromosome 3.

Kuozuka et al (1993) proved that the *rbcS* sequence of pRR1 (Xie and Wu 1988) showed 98.8% homology with the rice *rbcS* cDNA clone OSRUBPC1 (Matsuoka et al 1988). Wu et al (1986) indicated that two genes coding for rice *rbcS* share more than 95% DNA

sequence homology in a sequenced 230 bp segment, and one of the two cloned genes (pOSrbcS-1) was probably located on three chromosomes. Matsuoka et al (1988) also thought that a few genes encoded *rbcS* in rice from the Southern blot results, with the pOSSS1139 cDNA insert as a probe. Therefore, our result of physically mapping multipositions of *rbcS* on chromosomes is consistent with the above results.

Rice chromosomes are small and very difficult to identify individually, and all chromosomes have deeply stained regions on both sides of the centromere (Kurata and Omura 1978). This different Giemsa staining pattern makes it difficult to locate the true ends of the chromosomes and the relative chromosomal location of probes (Jiang et al 1995). We are going to continue to map the *phyA* and *rbcS* genes by multicolor fluorescence in situ hybridization with both gene clones and centromere-specific random fragment length polymorphism markers for special chromosomes.

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Fertility restoration studies in four WA CMS lines of rice

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Fertility restoration studies involving four wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—V20A, IR58025A, IR62829A, and IR54752A—resulted in the identification of 20 restorers. We studied segregation for fertility in the F₂ and backcross progenies of these CMS lines with four restorer lines—ARC11353, IR30864, IR13419-113-3, and IR9761-19-1. The results indicated that fertility restoration in WA CMS lines was controlled by two additive major genes. Their effect was sporophytic and they displayed differential gene interactions such as epistasis with complete dominance (12:3:1) or epistasis with incomplete dominance (9:6:1) depending on the parents involved in the cross.

We noticed differential segregation of the F₂ and backcross progenies in the crosses involving IR30864 and IR9761-19-1 depending on the female parent. This suggested that the performance and expressivity of the R genes varied according to the nuclear background of

the female parent. The pattern of segregation in crosses involving IR54752A was different from that of other CMS lines, suggesting the involvement of certain minor genes for fertility restoration carried by this CMS line in deciding the fertility of the progenies. ■

Effect of minor genes in restoration of fertility in CMS lines of rice

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We evaluated 128 hybrids in the 1994 dry season and 135 hybrids in the 1995 wet season. The hybrids, involving varieties C29 and PMK2, with different wild abortive (WA) sources of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—IR58025A, IR62829A, and PMS3A—showed marked differences in pollen and spikelet fertility. When C29 was crossed with IR62829A and PMS3A, it behaved as a partial restorer (21-90% pollen and spikelet fertility). But when crossed with IR58025A, it behaved as a maintainer (100% pollen and spikelet sterility). All three CMS lines, however, had WA cytoplasm. Similarly, PMK2 behaved as a restorer (>90% pollen and

spikelet fertility) with PMS3A, while it maintained sterility (100%) with IR62829A. The minor or modifier genes present in the pollinator might have reacted with the CMS lines used and resulted in this type of variation. ■

Breeding for male fertility restoration incorporating Basmati rice quality

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Basmati is the most highly valued rice commodity in the world agricultural trade market. Pusa Basmati 1, released in India, combines both high yield and ideal Basmati quality. In Pakistan, semi-tall Pak 385 and Pak 386 are reported to be better yielding than Basmati 370. Results at IARI have demonstrated the possibility of developing hybrids with Basmati grain quality and a high level of heterosis. Such Basmati hybrids would raise yields further.

A major limitation to developing Basmati rice hybrids is the nonavailability of satisfactory restoration among Basmati cultivars or breeding lines. Some 90% of Basmati materials showed imperfect maintaining ability, 3%